

The Effect of Employee Engagement and Career Development on Employee Performance Mediated By Work Motivation At Large Center for Training and Empowerment of Village Communities, Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration Yogyakarta

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to examine and analyze the effect of employee engagement and career development on employees mediated by work motivation at training centers and *empowerment of rural communities, disadvantaged areas and transmigration in Yogyakarta*. This study was applied to 55 respondents who are civil servants at the training and empowerment center for rural communities, disadvantaged areas and transmigration in Yogyakarta. In this study, all samples, namely Civil Servants, were used as respondents, so the sampling technique used was Census. "Tests in this study were carried out using the SmartPLS 3.3.3 software. And the research results are as follows: (1) Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, (2) Career Development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Career Development, Employee Engagement, Employee Performance, Work Motivation.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of human resources (HR) in the company is "to support the company's performance. A company cannot develop optimally if it is not supported by qualified and advanced human resources within the company. All companies or organizations strive to continuously improve employee performance so that the achievement of the vision and mission can be implemented immediately, including government employees. Performance is the result of a person's work that has been done legally in accordance with the responsibilities given to him in a certain period of time (Dessler, 2015). According to Wibasuri (2011), performance appraisal has an important role in increasing motivation at work. Performance appraisal is basically an important factor to develop an organization effectively and efficiently. In conducting the assessment, an analysis of the obstacles to the implementation of the work is carried out to obtain feedback and prepare recommendations for improvement and determine the results of the assessment. (Government of the Republic of Indonesia, 2011).

The Center for Training and Empowerment of Rural, Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration Communities (BBPPMDDTT) Yogyakarta as the "Central Technical Implementation Unit of the Esellon II Work Unit under the Agency for Human Resource Development and Empowerment of Village, Disadvantaged and Transmigration Communities (BBPPMDDTT) Yogyakarta in accordance with the Permendes Number 8 of 2017 has the task of implementing and training people from the specified field (Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, 2017)". Employees at BBPPMD always expect optimal work results with service to the community being the main thing for the organization. The performance of employees engaged in the service sector is increasingly showing weakness due to bureaucratic reform.

Based on an interview with the Head of Administration at BBPPMDDTT Yogyakarta, performance problems that occur in general are the lack of achievement of employee performance scores caused by lack of coordination between sections or substances, in addition to the problem of job transformation as well as employee placement that is not in accordance with the position. The following is the average assessment of employee work results at BBPPMDDTT Yogyakarta in 2018 from 2020.

Table 1. Average Assessment of Work Results in 2018 – 2020

Name	Year			Change	
	2018	2019	2020	2018-2019	2019-2020
EC	86.40	91.00	91.20	4.6	0.2
HS	81.85	83.33	83.60	1.48	0.27
CH	80.44	82.53	82.67	2.09	0.14
YK	79.95	80.59	80.75	0.64	0.16
NAC	80.44	80.44	80.52	0	0.08
TJ	80.36	80.60	80.84	0.24	0.24
PR	80.44	80.36	80.44	-0.08	0.08
LR	79.97	80.74	80.93	0.77	0.19
AW	79.92	80.44	80.52	0.52	0.08
FN	80.39	80.28	80.41	-0.11	0.13
EAV	84.00	82.24	82.98	-1.76	0.74
DO	81.60	81.76	82.78	0.16	1.02
AT	81.36	81.49	82.76	0.13	1.27
ADT	81.60	81.32	81.43	-0.28	0.11
BS	81.36	81.24	81.40	-0.12	0.16
GRP	81.36	87.27	84.27	5.91	-3
IK	86.53	83.57	82.04	-2.96	-1.53
LNA	82.56	81.79	82.04	-0.77	0.25
NEN	80.99	81.19	81.60	0.2	0.41
EBW	81.18	83.07	84.13	1.89	1.06
UM	80.91	82.48	82.56	1.57	0.08
RWF	83.60	81.68	82.16	-1.92	0.48
US	81.40	82.00	86.20	0.6	4.2
ICE	80,80	84.73	82.33	3.93	-2.4
Y	81.03	81.67	80.60	0.64	-1.07
LAW	82.40	81.49	80.54	-0.91	-0.95
YI	82.39	81.00	84.88	-1.39	3.88
PES	80,20	80.48	80.71	0.28	0.23
EBS	79.02	80.44	81.60	1.42	1.16
SH	80.60	84.56	83.16	3.96	-1,4
DL	79.28	80.61	82.73	1.33	2.12
Y	81.53	80.92	81.41	-0.61	0.49
DS	86.53	83.33	87.32	-3.2	3.99
AK	83.25	82.62	81.19	-0.63	-1.43
AI	77.07	81.25	81.21	4.18	-0.04
YES	76.73	81.11	81.19	4.38	0.08
PS	81.69	81.11	81.49	-0.58	0.38
WRP	81.00	81.33	81.59	0.33	0.26
RP	80.98	81.15	81.13	0.17	-0.02
BK	80.95	81.03	81.42	0.08	0.39
DP	80.14	81.15	81.04	1.01	-0.11
DSY	81.00	80,90	81.04	-0.1	0.14

Name	Year			Change	
	2018	2019	2020	2018-2019	2019-2020
YYP	80.80	81.11	80.51	0.31	-0.6
US	80.86	80.99	80.19	0.13	-0.8
AMW	80.68	80.43	81.08	-0.25	0.65
DEHK	80.76	81.00	80.74	0.24	-0.26
SNW	80.06	80.01	80.51	-0.05	0.5
SWHB	80.76	79.93	80.28	-0.83	0.35
VTD	80.08	79.93	80.28	-0.15	0.35
YES	79.68	79.93	80.28	0.25	0.35
SAN	80.69	79.60	80.28	-1.09	0.68

Source: Center for Village Community Training and Empowerment (2018, 2019, 2020)

Based on data on employee performance appraisal at BBPPMDDTT Yogyakarta, it can be seen that in the last 3 years employee performance has not consistently increased, some employees have actually experienced a decrease in value, which is indicated by a minus sign. This of course raises speculation that the employee's work results are not optimal. Based on the problems, phenomena that occur and the research gap, it is entitled "The Influence of Employee Engagement and Career Development on Employee Performance Mediated by Work Motivation at the Center for Training and Empowerment of Village Communities, Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration Yogyakarta".

THEORETICAL BASIS

Employee Performance

Performance is "the results of the work function of a person or group in a certain period of time that reflects how well the person or group fulfills the requirements of a job in an effort to achieve organizational goals. (Bernardin & Russell, 2013). According to As'ad (2011) Performance is the result achieved by a person according to the size applicable to the job in question. Increased individual performance (individual performance) will most likely also increase the company's performance (corporate performance) because the two have a close relationship.

Performance of Civil Servants (PNS)

According to Government Regulation Number 46 of 2011, employee performance or the same as work performance is the work achieved by every civil servant in organizational units in accordance with employee work goals and work behavior (Government of the Republic of Indonesia, 2011). In this Government Regulation, it is determined that the person authorized to make an assessment of the work performance of a civil servant is an appraising official, namely the direct supervisor of the civil servant concerned with the lowest provisions being an echelon V official or other designated official. The purpose of the work performance assessment is to ensure the objectivity of civil servant coaching which is carried out based on a work performance system and a career system that focuses on the work performance system. Performance appraisal is a series of performance management processes that start with the preparation of work performance planning in the form of Employee Work Targets (SKP), setting benchmarks covering aspects of quantity, quality, time, and cost of each job assignment activity. The implementation of the SKP assessment is carried out by comparing the realization of work with the targets that have been set. In conducting the assessment, an analysis of the obstacles to the implementation of the work is carried out to obtain feedback as well as develop recommendations for improvement and determine the results of the assessment. The results of the work performance assessment recommendations are used to improve organizational performance through improving work performance, potential development, and career of the civil servant concerned as well as developing management, organization, and work environment.

Employee Engagement

The definition of Employee Engagement is a sense of attachment to the organization and their work emotionally, able to provide the best ability in terms of helping the success of a series of tangible benefits for individuals and organizations (McLeod & Clarke,

2009). According to Maylett and Warner (2014) Employee engagement is a condition or condition in which there is a sense of enthusiasm, energy, commitment and passion from employees towards their work.

Career development

As quoted in Osibanjo and Adeniji (2012), the term “career” has a different meaning for each person. Wilensky (1961) defines it as the success of related work regulated in organizational rules, where people move in an orderly sequence. Wilensky (1961) View a career as a design, tailored for the individual to run and ultimately predictable. However, Leach and Chakiris (1988) Looking at careers in a deeper perspective, they argue that careers are a by-product of work and work is an individual activity, with the acquisition of continuous payouts with predictable goals.

Work motivation

According to Robbins and Judge (2015), Motivation is "the willingness to exert a high level of effort toward organizational goals, conditioned by the effort of ability to satisfy the same individual need." Where as according to M Hasibuan (2017) Motivation is the provision of a driving force that creates enthusiasm for one's work so that they want to work with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

Employee engagement is a sense of attachment to the organization and their work emotionally, capable and motivated to give their best in terms of helping the success of a series of tangible benefits for individuals and organizations (McLeod in Lubis & Wulandari, 2018). According to Maylett & Winner in Vellya, Pio, and Rumawas (2020) Employee engagement is a condition or condition in which there is a sense of enthusiasm, energy, commitment and passion from employees towards their work. If the employee enjoys his involvement with the company then he will enjoy his time at work to carry out these activities, he will use his work time effectively and optimally and his work performance will be high as well.

H1: Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance

Career development can be seen from various approaches; match between career development, individual personality, and their job (Parsons, 1909) and processes for achieving specific organizational and employee goals (Kirk et al., 2000). Osibanjo and Adeniji (2012) argues that career development can help reduce the costs incurred to recruit and train new employees in the organization. High career development in organizations can increase and foster high employee performance in employees (SP Robbins & Judge, 2015).

H2: Career Development has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance

According to Robbins and Judge (2015) Motivation is the desire to use a high level of energy from its efforts to achieve organizational goals, which is conditioned by the ability to satisfy several individual goals. Where as *employee engagement* is a sense of attachment to the organization and their work emotionally, capable and motivated to give their best in terms of helping the success of a series of tangible benefits for individuals and organizations. (McLeod in Lubis & Wulandari, 2018). According to Maylett & Winner in Vellya et al. (2020) Employee engagement is a condition or condition in which there is a sense of enthusiasm, energy, commitment and passion from employees towards their work. If employees feel themselves in the company enjoying their time, it will increase employee work results.

H3: Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Work Motivation

According to Robbins and Judge (2015), Motivation is “the desire to use a high level of effort to achieve organizational goals, conditioned by the ability to satisfy some individual goal. Whereas career development can be seen from various approaches; match between career development, individual personality, and their job (Parsons, 1909) and processes for achieving specific organizational and employee goals, Kirk, Downey, Duckett, and Woody (2000) and Osibanjo and Adeniji (2012) argues that career development can help reduce the costs incurred to recruit and train new employees in the organization. High career development in organizations can increase and foster high employee performance in employees (SP Robbins & Judge, 2015).

H4: Career Development has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through Work Motivation

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is included in quantitative research with survey method. The survey method is used to obtain data from certain natural (not artificial) places whose data is collected using questionnaires, tests, structured interviews, and so on.(Sugiyono, 2016). Based on the level of naturalness, this research uses survey research methods. The survey method is used to get data from certain natural places, but the researcher conducts research with questionnaires and structured interviews. This research was conducted at the Yogyakarta Transmigration Center for Latohan, which is located at Jalan Parasamya No.16 Beran, Beran Kidul, Tridadi, Sleman District, Sleman Regency, Special Region of Yogyakarta.The population in this study is the Civil Servants (PNS) BBPMDDDT Yogyakarta, amounting to 55 people. Details of the class positions of BBPMDDDTT Yogyakarta employees can be seen in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Class of BBPMDDTT Yogyakarta Employees

No	Field Type	Amount
1	Ka. Hall	1
2	Head of Administration	2
3	Village Community Training Coordinator	1
4	Facilitation Coordinator and Empowerment Assistance	1
5	Coordinator of Mentoring & Empowerment Model Implementation	1
6	Head of Planning, Program & Training Subdivision	1
7	Head of General Subdivision	1
8	General Functional Position	17
9	Sub coordinator	30
Total		55

Source: Yogyakarta BBPMDD Secondary Data, 2021

RESEARCH RESULT

Outer Model Measurement Test Results

The division of "outer model by testing convergent validity, discriminant validity, average variance extracted (AVE), composite reliability, and cronbach alpha".

Convergent Validity

The value of convergent validity is an assessment with the intention of an adequate initial and developmental stage (Ghozali & Latan, 2018).

Table 3. Convergent Validity

Variable	Items	Outer Loading	Criteria	Information
<i>Employee Engagement(X1)</i>	X1.1	0.931	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.2	0.920	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.3	0.928	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.4	0.879	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.5	0.909	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.6	0.845	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.7	0.937	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.8	0.905	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.9	0.878	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.10	0.899	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.11	0.920	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.12	0.856	> 0.7	Valid

Variable	Items	Outer Loading	Criteria	Information
	X1.13	0.933	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.14	0.919	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.15	0.860	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.16	0.884	> 0.7	Valid
	X1.17	0.886	> 0.7	Valid
Career Development(X2)	X2.1	0.932	> 0.7	Valid
	X2.2	0.850	> 0.7	Valid
	X2.3	0.917	> 0.7	Valid
	X2.4	0.812	> 0.7	Valid
	X2.5	0.824	> 0.7	Valid
	X2.6	0.910	> 0.7	Valid
Work motivation (Z)	Z1	0.835	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.2	0.838	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.3	0.847	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.4	0.815	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.5	0.827	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.6	0.840	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.7	0.893	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.8	0.847	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.9	0.857	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.10	0.806	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.11	0.917	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.12	0.857	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.13	0.867	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.14	0.799	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.15	0.868	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.16	0.861	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.17	0.910	> 0.7	Valid
	Z.18	0.856	> 0.7	Valid
Employee Performance (Y)	Y1	0.869	> 0.7	Valid
	Y2	0.869	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.3	0.892	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.4	0.881	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.5	0.866	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.6	0.913	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.7	0.849	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.8	0.906	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.9	0.904	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.10	0.921	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.11	0.888	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.12	0.933	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.13	0.870	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.14	0.910	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.15	0.889	> 0.7	Valid

Variable	Items	Outer Loading	Criteria	Information
	Y.16	0.901	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.17	0.904	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.18	0.934	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.19	0.883	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.20	0.873	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.21	0.922	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.22	0.901	> 0.7	Valid
	Y.23	0.915	> 0.7	Valid

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the value of the outer loading item for each latent variable is > 0.7 so that the research instrument is said to meet convergent validity.

Discriminant Validity

The value of the cross loading factor with the use of the selection variable can be seen in Table 4:

Table 4. Discriminant Validity Test Results

	<i>Employee Engagement</i>	<i>Career Development</i>	<i>Work motivation</i>	<i>Employee Performance</i>
X1.1	0.931	0.731	0.755	0.797
X1.2	0.920	0.718	0.685	0.835
X1.3	0.928	0.695	0.729	0.792
X1.4	0.879	0.699	0.709	0.758
X1.5	0.909	0.764	0.707	0.847
X1.6	0.845	0.648	0.736	0.786
X1.7	0.937	0.751	0.736	0.853
X1.8	0.905	0.723	0.709	0.777
X1.9	0.878	0.711	0.711	0.777
X1.10	0.899	0.744	0.743	0.799
X1.11	0.920	0.756	0.711	0.864
X1.12	0.856	0.674	0.762	0.806
X1.13	0.933	0.787	0.722	0.842
X1.14	0.919	0.774	0.756	0.791
X1.15	0.860	0.761	0.726	0.794
X1.16	0.884	0.788	0.706	0.852
X1.17	0.886	0.725	0.749	0.803
X2.1	0.920	0.932	0.729	0.816
X2.2	0.928	0.850	0.697	0.741
X2.3	0.879	0.917	0.689	0.813
X2.4	0.909	0.812	0.783	0.804
X2.5	0.845	0.824	0.636	0.691
X2.6	0.937	0.910	0.651	0.725
Z1	0.638	0.666	0.835	0.709
Z.2	0.737	0.621	0.838	0.722
Z.3	0.638	0.673	0.847	0.670
Z.4	0.624	0.632	0.815	0.693

	<i>Employee Engagement</i>	<i>Career Development</i>	Work motivation	Employee Performance
Z.5	0.650	0.664	0.827	0.703
Z.6	0.745	0.716	0.840	0.808
Z.7	0.691	0.702	0.893	0.787
Z.8	0.680	0.640	0.847	0.693
Z.9	0.663	0.635	0.857	0.723
Z.10	0.625	0.564	0.806	0.673
Z.11	0.710	0.740	0.917	0.805
Z.12	0.724	0.740	0.857	0.823
Z.13	0.730	0.671	0.867	0.787
Z.14	0.604	0.642	0.799	0.666
Z.15	0.665	0.772	0.868	0.735
Z.16	0.756	0.694	0.861	0.762
Z.17	0.723	0.726	0.910	0.835
Z.18	0.756	0.758	0.856	0.831
Y1	0.805	0.735	0.795	0.869
Y2	0.767	0.805	0.817	0.869
Y.3	0.824	0.740	0.811	0.892
Y.4	0.803	0.718	0.689	0.881
Y.5	0.798	0.781	0.860	0.866
Y.6	0.807	0.757	0.726	0.913
Y.7	0.747	0.756	0.772	0.849
Y.8	0.819	0.763	0.753	0.906
Y.9	0.815	0.787	0.843	0.904
Y.10	0.840	0.837	0.785	0.921
Y.11	0.768	0.795	0.794	0.888
Y.12	0.852	0.794	0.764	0.933
Y.13	0.780	0.781	0.762	0.870
Y.14	0.810	0.821	0.761	0.910
Y.15	0.808	0.829	0.851	0.889
Y.16	0.788	0.757	0.731	0.901
Y.17	0.854	0.804	0.860	0.904
Y.18	0.839	0.801	0.762	0.934
Y.19	0.748	0.839	0.768	0.883
Y.20	0.802	0.755	0.798	0.873
Y.21	0.833	0.833	0.765	0.922
Y.22	0.844	0.815	0.857	0.901
Y.23	0.802	0.773	0.740	0.915

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the table above, it can be seen that "the value of the cross loading factor of each indicator on the variable is greater than the value of the cross loading factor with other variables. Thus, this research instrument has met the criteria of good discriminant validity so that it can be used for further research and analysis.

Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

In addition to observing the cross loading value, the validity test can also be known through other methods, namely by looking at the average variance extracted (AVE) value. The AVE value is used to measure the amount of variance that can be captured by the

construct compared to the variance caused by measurement errors. Ghozali (2014:45) recommends the use of AVE for a criterion in assessing convergent validity. An AVE value of at least 0.5 indicates a good measure of convergent validity. That is, latent variables can explain the average of more than half the variance of the indicators. The AVE value of this study can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. AVE. Value

Variable	Criteria	AVE . value
<i>Employee Engagement(X1)</i>	> 0.5	0.810
<i>Career Development(X2)</i>	> 0.5	0.766
Work Motivation (Z)	> 0.5	0.727
Employee Performance (Y)	> 0.5	0.802

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the test results above, it can be seen that "the AVE value of each variable has a value > 0.5. This shows that each variable can be declared valid, so it can be used for further research.

Composite Reliability

The research instrument that measures a reliable statement variable with Cronbach's alpha assessment is above 0.70 (Ghozali, 2011). The results of the composite reliability calculation are considered, namely Table 6.

Table 6. Composite Reliability

Variable	Criteria	Composite Reliability
<i>Employee Engagement(X1)</i>	>0.7	0.986
<i>Career Development(X2)</i>	>0.7	0.989
Work Motivation (Z)	>0.7	0.980
Employee Performance (Y)	>0.7	0.989

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

From Table 6, it can be seen that "the value of the composite reliability of each variable has a value > 0.7. This shows that each variable is declared reliable and can be used for further research and analysis.

Cronbach Alpha

To strengthen the results of the reliability test, Cronbach's alpha value is also used. Where a variable can be declared reliable if it has a Cronbach alpha value 0.7 for confirmatory research and Cronbach alpha 0.6 - 0.7 is still acceptable for exploratory research.(Ghozali & Latan, 2015). The results of the calculation of Cronbach's alpha can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Criteria	Cronbach's Alpha
<i>Employee Engagement(X1)</i>	>0.7	0.985
<i>Career Development(X2)</i>	>0.7	0.938
Work Motivation (Z)	>0.7	0.978
Employee Performance (Y)	>0.7	0.989

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Table 7 shows that each variable can be declared reliable, so it can be used for further research and analysis.

Inner Model Measurement Model Test Results

In the measurement section of the inner model, the following models will be used: the Goodness-of-Fit Test and the Path Coefficient Test.

Goodness of Fit

Testing of the structural model is done by looking at the value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) which is the goodness-fit test of the model. The value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) in the PLS Algorithm report can be seen by selecting R Square (Ghozali et al, 2015). The following is the R^2 value in this study:

Table 8. Coefficient of Determination

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Work Motivation (Z)	0.840	0.837
Employee Performance (Y)	0.954	0.952

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on Table 8, it can be seen that the coefficient of determination of the work motivation variable is 0.840, meaning that the model's ability to explain the motivation variable is $0.840 = 84.0\%$. And the coefficient of determination of employee performance is 0.954, meaning that the regression model of the factors that affect employee performance is 95.4%.

Path Coefficient

Figure 1. Path Coefficient Results

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2022

Based on Figure 1, it can be seen that the largest path coefficient assessment shows the largest influence with a value of 4,331 on the effect of employee engagement on work motivation. Meanwhile, for the smallest value, the effect of employee engagement on employee performance is 1,571.

Hypothesis test

Intended for testing each hypothesis with a PLS analysis study of the implementation of the t-test, each of which affects the partial.

Live Effect Test

Table 9. Bootstrapping Results Direct Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Employee Engagement > Employee Performance	0.409	0.417	0.090	4,571	0.000
Career Development > Employee Performance	0.297	0.299	0.097	3.069	0.002

Source: Primary Data processed, 2022

From Table 9 the test results show that "the original sample value of employee engagement on employee performance has a value of 0.409 with a significance of 0.000. This result means that employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. H1 is accepted. And the test results show that the original sample career development value on employee performance has a value of 0.297 with a significance of 0.002. These results mean that career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. H2 is accepted".

Indirect Effect Test

Table 10. Bootstrapping Results Indirect Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Employee Engagement > Work Motivation > Employee Performance	0.143	0.137	0.061	2,346	0.019
Career Development > Work Motivation > Employee Performance	0.132	0.129	0.065	2,031	0.043

Source: Primary Data processed, 2022

In table 10 the test results show that the value of "original sample employee engagement on employee performance through work motivation has a value of 0.143 with a significance of 0.019. This result means that employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work motivation. H3 is accepted. And in the table the test results show that the original sample career development value on employee performance through work motivation has a value of 0.132 with a significance of 0.043. These results mean that career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work motivation. H4 is accepted".

DISCUSSION

Employee Engagement has a positive effect on employee performance

Employee Engagement based on the results of hypothesis testing, the results of the analysis have a value of 0.409 with a significance of 0.000. These results prove that "employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Employee engagement or employees' sense of attachment to their work or organization is very important for the organization and is a determining factor behind the high and low business performance of a company (Fisher, 2007). Ajai Singh as a master trainer for Transformasi Indonesia stated that employee engagement is a psychological statement in which employees feel interested in determining the success of the company and have a strong desire and motivation to perform beyond their obligations.

Career development has a positive effect on employee performance

Based on the results hypothesis testing obtained the results of "analysis has a value of 0.143 with a significance of 0.019. These results prove that career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. According to DuBrin (2014) "Career development is an employment activity that helps employees plan their future careers in the company so that the company and the employees concerned can develop themselves to the maximum". In research conducted by Nguyen, Mai, and Nguyen (2014), namely those that affect the acquisition of development or personal planning of the existing situation.

Employee Engagement has a positive effect on employee performance through work motivation

Based on the results Hypothesis testing obtained the results of the analysis has a value of 0.297 with a significance of 0.002. These results prove that "employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work motivation. Vogel et al. (2016) defines employee engagement as a sense of enthusiasm and loyalty of an employee at work to carry out tasks well so as to improve company performance. Schaufeli, Salanova, González-Romá, and Bakker (2002) states that there are three characteristics in employee engagement, namely vigor, dedication, and absorption. Yin (2017) Explaining performance is an assessment of the results of work carried out by employees according to the specified time. Vogel et al. (2016) defines performance as an assessment and evaluation of the work of employees by the organization which is carried out at a certain time, for the achievement of organizational goals. Employee performance can be divided into 6 dimensions which include: effort quantity, quality, job knowledge, compliance with rules, interpersonal competence" (Viswesvaran, 1993).

Career Development has a positive effect on Employee Performance through Work Motivation

Based on the hypothesis obtained the results of the analysis have a value of 0.132 with a significance of 0.043. These results prove that career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work motivation. There are many things that will affect a person's work results, with the career development of his workers (Rivai in Febriansyah, 2016). Career development is a process of increasing the work ability of an employee that encourages increased performance in order to achieve the desired career. Career development supported by the company, expects feedback from employees in the form of good performance. According to Marwansyah (2014: 208) career development are self-development activities taken by a person to realize his personal career plan. Research conducted by Pratiwi (2015) found that career development has a positive effect on employee performance."

CONCLUSION

1. Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance of the Center for Training and Empowerment of Village Communities, Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration Yogyakarta.
2. Career development has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the Central Community Training and Empowerment Center for Rural, Disadvantaged and Transmigration Communities in Yogyakarta.
3. *Employee Engagement* positive and significant effect on Employee Performance mediated by Work Motivation Center for Training and Empowerment of Village Communities, Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration Yogyakarta.
4. Career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance which is mediated by work motivation at the Center for Training and Empowerment of Village Communities, Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration of Yogyakarta.

SUGGESTION

Based on the description in the previous chapters, the suggestions that can be given are:

1. In the path coefficient test, the smallest effect is shown by the effect of employee engagement on employee performance of 1,571. Based on this, the researcher suggests that companies should improve employee engagement in order to improve their performance. This can be done by involving employees in the preparation of company policies, this is considered effective because the employee's sense of attachment to the company will be greater because they feel they have.
2. This research also has many limitations, both in terms of the number of variables, the number of respondents, and the scope of respondents. Therefore, the researcher recommends the next researcher to expand the scope of his research so that he can form better research results.

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